

Contributi/3

The Issue of Statistics in Medicine in the Era of the Fever Crisis:

Pierre-Charles-Alexandre Louis and the Numerical School*

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With the advent of artificial intelligence and its extensive use of statistics in clinical practice, ethical and epistemic challenges in applying statistical methods have become increasingly significant. Issues include preventing statistics from producing merely correlative knowledge lacking causality, ensuring meaningful patient care, preserving patient individuality, and balancing qualitative and quantitative aspects. However, these concerns are not new. This article argues that P-C-A Louis's 19th-century systematic use of statistics produced an epistemological rupture in medicine, fundamentally transforming clinical practice. The study examines the role of hospitals in promoting statistics, presents Louis's doctrine, and summarizes the favorable reception of his ideas, alongside contemporary debates and criticisms regarding the numerical method. I suggest that Louis's epistemological rupture is pivotal to understanding contemporary biomedicine due to three main features of his doctrine: methodologically, as statistics became the main scientific method for medicine; therapeutically-clinically, as patient individuality was significantly diminished; and epistemically, as, for the sake of comparison, qualitative aspects were reduced to quantitative ones.

1. Introduction: One Statistic, Many Statistics

Today, discussing clinical practice without reference to statistics has become nearly impossible.

The widespread adoption of big data and artificial intelligence, both of which rely extensively on statistical methods, along with the prospects laid out in articles about AI in surgery,¹ makes the question regarding the limits

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of statistical applications in medicine particularly significant. In medicine, concerns surrounding statistics extend beyond ethical considerations and are fundamentally epistemic. In other words, can statistics be employed without producing merely correlative knowledge? Furthermore, how can statistical methods be employed while ensuring their meaningfulness and relevance for patient care? Can the use of statistics preserve the uniqueness of each patient and maintain an appropriate balance between qualitative and quantitative factors? These questions are not new. Statistics have long been a part of medical practice, and historians have extensively documented physicians' discussions regarding their use – and misuse. However, only at a certain historical juncture did statistics become recognized as a defining feature of medical scientificity. Although statistics were commonly employed in medical practice as early as the 17th and early 18th centuries, statistical methods did not constitute a formal scientific approach before the 19th century.

For instance, in the 17th century, W. Petty, in his *Essay Concerning the Growth of the City of London*², attempted to outline a «mathematical history of humanity». Around the same period, J. Graunt produced one of the earliest critical analyses of mortality records in his *Bills of Mortality*,³ connecting mortality data to governance, religion, commerce, population growth, and disease in London. Similarly, T. Nettleton⁴ calculated mortality rates associated with smallpox inoculation, while in the 18th century, J. Jurin⁵ established the first data collection network on smallpox deaths in England.⁶ Overall, efforts aimed at preventing smallpox significantly promoted the statistical evaluation of inoculation's therapeutic effectiveness. As U. Tröhler rightly notes, these early English examples in enumeration of smallpox are «an example of an unconsciously expressed informal probabilistic statement, implying a mode of probabilistic thinking»⁷. This interpretation aligns with G. Fordyce's effort to organize clinical histories of London patients in tables and records. Although Fordyce's work may be viewed retrospectively as anticipating evidence-based medicine, he combined statistical data with chemical and physiological analyses without adopting strict methodological standardization. For instance, he did not calculate probabilities or average survival rates, and he relied primarily on

¹ See, for instance, H. Saeidi, et al., *Autonomous robotic laparoscopic surgery for intestinal anastomosis*, «Science Robotics», 7, eabj2908, 2022; for a more general account of the use of statistics in AI, see S. Friedrich et al., *Is there a role for statistics in artificial intelligence?*, «Advances in Data Analysis and Classification», 16, 2022, pp. 823-846.

² W. Petty, *Another essay in political arithmetick, concerning the growth of the city of London*, London 1683.

³ J. Graunt, *Natural and Political Observations Made upon the Bills of Mortality*, London 1662.

⁴ T. Nettleton, *Part of a letter from Dr. Nettleton, concerning the inoculation of the smallpox*, «Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London», 32, 1722, pp. 209-212.

⁵ J. Jurin, *An Account of the Success of Inoculating the Small-Pox in Great Britain*, London 1724.

⁶ A. Bird, *James Jurin and the avoidance of bias in collecting and assessing evidence on the effects of variolation*, «Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine», 112, 3, 2019, pp. 119-123.

⁷ U. Tröhler, *Probabilistic thinking and evaluation of therapies: An introductory overview*, «Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine», 113, 7, 2020, pp. 274-277.

descriptive rather than analytical explanations for physiological phenomena, including inflammation theories. Thus, his approach can be more accurately described as proto-statistical⁸. Similarly, on the European continent, numerous authors also turned to statistics to support medical research. Beyond the aforementioned contributions of J. Jurin and T. Nettleton, E. Duvillard extensively addressed the potential impact of vaccination on population longevity⁹. D. Bernoulli¹⁰ conducted mathematical studies on smallpox, as did C. M. de La Condamine¹¹. Nevertheless, as G. Canguilhem points out, many of these French works predominantly consisted of observational compilations intended to support specific theoretical claims rather than employing statistics as an independent scientific method¹². In other words, statistics was used to compare public health data – for instance, the effectiveness of therapies in particular climates or mortality rates under specific social conditions – but were not yet central to establishing medicine’s scientific character. Even in the 1820s, figures such as B. F. Hawkins¹³ were employing statistics to study public health issues, but medicine did not rely primarily upon statistics. In the 18th century, following Canguilhem’s reasoning, statistics represented merely one of several analytical tools available to physicians when theorizing about particular medical conditions affecting populations¹⁴. In other words, although statistics played a significant role in comparing mortality rates, disease patterns, or the

⁸ G. Fordyce, *An attempt to improve the evidence of medicine in Transactions of a Society for the Improvement of Medical and Chirurgical Knowledge*, London 1793.

⁹ E.E. Duvillard, *Analyse et tableaux de l’influence de la petite vérole sur la mortalité à chaque âge*. Paris 1806.

¹⁰ D. Bernoulli, *Essai d’une nouvelle analyse de la mortalité causée par la petite vérole*, in *Mémoire de Mathématique et de Physique*, Paris 1766.

¹¹ C.M. de La Condamine, *Mémoire sur l’inoculation de la petite vérole*. Paris 1754 (revisited in 1758 and again in 1765 with new data). On this see also G. Canguilhem, *La statistique médicale en France dans la 1^{re} moitié du XIX^e siècle*, CAPHES GC 24.9.10, 1963.

¹² G. Canguilhem, *La statistique médicale*, p. 1.

¹³ B.F. Hawkins, *Elements of Medical Statistics*, London 1829.

¹⁴ Here, Canguilhem suggested two distinct ways of using statistics: «in the service of Theory» and «in the service of Research». By «Statistics in the Service of Theory,» I refer to the practice of using statistics as a supportive tool for existing or emerging theoretical frameworks. Physicians collect numerical data to reinforce or refine broader medical theories, rather than employing statistics as an independent investigative method. This approach involves gathering numbers to compare health conditions, evaluate therapies, or investigate mortality rates, but the data themselves do not form a standalone research methodology. Instead, they serve to confirm or illustrate an overarching conceptual understanding of disease, public health, or treatment efficacy. In this model, statistical procedures typically emphasize descriptive quantification rather than formal hypothesis testing or inference, feeding into a broader theoretical narrative about health and illness. By contrast, «Statistics in the Service of Research» denotes a scenario in which statistical methods become the primary drivers of scientific inquiry. This marks a shift toward an empirical, data-driven mindset, where statistical analysis reveals patterns, correlations, and causal inferences, often without the direct guidance of a pre-existing theory. Here, statistics serves not merely as a descriptive instrument but as a foundational methodology for evaluating medical interventions, testing hypotheses, and establishing clinical evidence. In this model, statistical reasoning plays a central role in shaping what is recognized as valid medical knowledge, with particular emphasis on controlled comparisons, sample representativeness, and inferential reasoning.

effectiveness of therapies across various environments, statistics was not yet a key component in medicine's claim to scientific legitimacy. Instead, statistics remained an ancillary tool rather than a fundamental scientific method. This status changed only at the beginning of the 19th century, particularly during the severe fever epidemics in Europe. At that time, the French numerical school, led by Pierre-Charles-Alexandre Louis, shifted the function of statistics from descriptive summaries of medical phenomena to analytical methods capable of guiding clinical decisions¹⁵. This development was key to establishing statistics as a rigorous analytical approach for assessing therapeutic effectiveness. In this article, I argue that Pierre-Charles-Alexandre Louis's systematic use of statistics in medicine sparked what G. Bachelard would define as an epistemological rupture¹⁶.

To support this argument, the first section briefly explains the historical role of hospitals as crucial institutions in facilitating the integration of statistics into medical practice. The second section introduces Louis's key ideas and provides selected bibliographic considerations, particularly because his publications had limited circulation. The third section examines the reception of Louis's ideas, with particular attention to the contribution made by Jules Gavarret. Following this, the article briefly addresses contemporary debates on the statistical foundations of the numerical method.

I contend that Louis's work is crucial for re-evaluating the contemporary debate about the use of statistics in medicine because the epistemological rupture introduced by the numerical school still echoes in many contemporary biomedical methods, which extensively rely on statistics. Louis's influence in contemporary biomedicine largely results from the widespread adoption of Louis's methods in North America beginning in the 19th century. The idea that French numerical medicine constituted a distinct and autonomous development

¹⁵ Two questions may arise: What enabled this shift, and why did it happen in France? Furthermore, if we consider the thesis of both A. Bird (*Systematicity, knowledge, and bias: How systematicity made clinical medicine a science*, «Synthese», 196, pp. 863-879) and U. Tröhler (*To Improve the Evidence of Medicine: The 18th Century British Origins of a Critical Approach*, Edinburgh 2000), who argue that statistics as a scientific method was already used in the United Kingdom in the 18th century, what is the specificity of the French numerical school? These questions can be answered from socio-political and institutional perspectives – the creation of hospitals as places of care and their unique organization in France – or from an academic one: French numerical theory circulated in North America more extensively than English statistical doctrines (see W. Osler, *The influence of Louis on American medicine*, «The Johns Hopkins Hospital Bulletin», 77-78, (August–September), 1897; E. Bartlett *An Essay on the Philosophy of Medical Science*, Philadelphia 1842; J. Jackson jr., *Cases of Cholera Collected at Paris in the Month of April 1832*, Boston 1832; O.W. Holmes, *The contagiousness of puerperal fever*, «New England Quarterly Journal of Medicine and Surgery», 1843, pp. 503-530; G. Hinsdale, *The American medical argonauts pupils of Pierre-Charles-Alexandre Louis*, «Transactions and Studies of the College of Physicians of Philadelphia», 13, 1945, pp. 37-43; R.U. Massey, *Pierre Louis and his numerical method*, «Connecticut Medicine», 53, 1983, p. 613; W.R. Steiner, *Dr. Pierre-Charles-Alexandre Louis, a distinguished Parisian teacher of American medical students*, «Annals of Medical History», 2, 6, 1940, pp. 451-460).

¹⁶ G. Bachelard, *The Formation of the Scientific Mind*, London 1986 [1938].

– unlike concurrent European practices – and thus represented an epistemological rupture depends both on historical and structural factors (such as the emergence of hospitals and public health administration) and on epistemic factors (such as anatomical-pathological methods already established in French hospitals).

My contention that Louis's numerical medicine was the trigger for this epistemic shift rests on highlighting the following three transformations:

1. **Methodological Change:** Within numerical medicine, the method itself guarantees the scientific status of medicine, with statistics serving as the primary instrument of scientific investigation.
2. **Therapeutic-Clinical Change:** A new conception of the patient emerges, who is characterized not as an individual with unique attributes but as a standardized clinical case.
3. **Epistemic Change:** In close relation to the second transformation, the numerical approach alters the relationship between qualitative and quantitative elements. To achieve genuine comparability, data must be homogeneous, necessitating the conversion of qualitative characteristics into quantifiable measures¹⁷.

This text aims to examine Louis's contributions and the historical context in which the numerical method emerged in order to illustrate how statistics influenced the medical practices of the 19th century and to inform current discussions concerning the role of statistics in biomedicine. As this discussion explores potential links without investigating them extensively, further research into connections between these early statistical practices and contemporary medicine remains necessary.

2. Hospital and Statistics: Statistics as Support for Biopolitics and as Its Result

There are two important reasons that made Louis's numerical medicine one of the earliest clinical practices grounded in statistics: First, the anatomico-pathological tradition (represented by figures like A. Chomel and G. Andral), in which Louis himself was trained. Second, numerical medicine emerged within

¹⁷ Sabina Leonelli's book *La ricerca scientifica nell'era dei Big Data* [Scientific Research in the Era of Big Data] (Milano 2018) is especially relevant when it comes to the issue of data heterogeneity. Leonelli argues that Big Data bring together different types of data from various sources, linking them in ways that create connections between fields and approaches that wouldn't normally interact. Leonelli's key idea is that the sheer volume of data available today is pushing science away from a theory-driven approach and toward a more data-driven one. From this perspective, I think the same concept applies to Louis's approach. Likewise, the challenges of contemporary epistemology that Leonelli highlights – such as inconsistencies in classification methods that could lead to incommensurability, the way data quality affects research outcomes, the inevitable partiality of collected data, and concerns about data reliability – also seem relevant to Louis's research.

the institutional framework of early 19th-century French healthcare, particularly through publicly funded hospitals controlled by state or municipal authorities and associated directly with medical schools.

By the late 1820s, as numerical medicine began to develop, hospitals already occupied a central role in public health management and the training of physicians¹⁸. This 19th-century hospital system had its roots in the reforms introduced during the French Revolution. Before the Revolution, public health relied primarily on three types of institutions:

1. Hospitals, which served diverse populations, including individuals with disabilities or chronic illnesses, elderly people, abandoned children, and the sick; these institutions also distributed basic provisions, such as food and clothing, and provided elementary education to impoverished children.
2. The *hôtels-dieu*, typically located in urban areas, which admitted exclusively sick individuals but commonly excluded those classified as insane as well as persons with leprosy, venereal diseases, syphilis, and pregnant women.
3. General hospitals, established in the 17th century primarily to confine beggars, which accommodated poor populations and patients not accepted by the *hôtels-dieu*.

Following the Revolution, a significant reorganization of healthcare institutions occurred, dividing patient care between hospitals – absorbing the majority of former *hôtels-dieu* – and hospices, designated primarily for impoverished individuals and beggars. Hospitals continued receiving public funds, cared exclusively for the sick (with the notable exception of persons considered *incurable*)¹⁹, and became essential training grounds for new doctors. This administrative division enabled greater efficiency, transforming hospitals from mere shelters into active centers for medical research, innovation, and education. Consequently, hospital medicine shifted from passively observing diseases to actively intervening to alter their progression²⁰. M. Foucault analyzed this transformation, highlighting its (bio)political implications concerning healthcare administration and social control²¹.

However, the function of hospitals extended beyond social control and included the production of new medical knowledge. Hospitals began to require bedside teaching for medical students, which involved gathering significant

¹⁸ It is no coincidence that when M. Foucault (*The Birth of the Clinic*, London 1973) discusses scientific clinical practice – founded on post-mortem anatomical investigations, the observation of symptoms in vivo, and the systematic recording of symptom frequency in connection with specific lesions – he always refers to a hospital environment.

¹⁹ At that time the ‘incurable’ is as the insane, syphilitics, epileptics, pregnant women among others, who were organized in separate and dedicated establishments.

²⁰ The 19th century marked the first widespread application of pharmacology in patient care; see the fundamental work of Giovanni Semmola (1853) on pharmacology and William Green Morton’s discovery of ether as an anesthetic.

²¹ M. Foucault, *Madness and Civilization*, New York 1965.

numbers of patients, now categorized as individual clinical cases, under direct supervision by physicians and trainees. Prior to the institutionalization of hospitals, treatment typically took place in private homes, where physicians visited patients who received care from family members. Patients and physicians were dispersed geographically. After hospitals became established, however, individuals displaying similar symptoms could be gathered in a single location, allowing physicians to collaborate by comparing cases. It is no coincidence that G. Canguilhem argued that, with the rise of hospitalization, patients effectively turned into ‘cases’. Their individual lives were standardized within the new spatial framework of the hospital ward. Indeed, for the first time, hospital care was governed by formal protocols, placed under a hierarchical medical structure, and documented most aspects of a patient’s stay²².

In 19th-century France, hospitals served simultaneously as centers for public health management and as training institutions for new physicians²³. This distinctive arrangement facilitated the systematic use of statistical methods. The organizational structure of hospitals provided two crucial advantages for statistical analysis. First, it enabled physicians to group patients according to common symptoms, achieving preliminary standardization. Second, it allowed continuous disease monitoring through extensive data collection. Consequently, categorizing patients by symptoms, age, geographic origin, and gender laid the theoretical and practical groundwork necessary for gathering pathological data, comparing clinical cases, and identifying reliable patterns in disease occurrence. Even P. Pinel, who opposed numerical medicine, recognized the hospital’s key role as a data hub. In his *Traité médico-philosophique sur l’aliénation mentale*, Pinel noted that the design of a hospital reflects the logic of classification. For instance, he organized the Salpêtrière Hospital into departments, grouping patients according to symptomatology and stages of illness, thus facilitating the administration of comparable treatments to similar clinical cases²⁴.

Ultimately, both proponents and critics of the numerical method agreed that hospitals provided the optimal environment for observing and comparing large numbers of patients, thereby enabling comprehensive data collection and analysis. Furthermore, hospitals were structured not only by methodological logic but also increasingly by economic rationality, a convergence that became evident during the 19th century. As healthcare transitioned from private to public financing, hospitals faced new demands for operational efficiency, an issue that was previously overlooked. By rationalizing services, standardizing patient care, and implementing stringent administrative oversight – progressively measured

²² G. Canguilhem, *La statistique médicale*, p. 4.

²³ For instance, if we consider English situation at the end of the 18th century and the very beginning of the 19th century, we still find hospitals that are charitable care for the poor sustained by private entities and donation, while general practitioners and dispensaries played the primary role in medical treatment visiting patient at home. In addition, at this very moment in England medical school remained separated from hospitals.

²⁴ P. Pinel, *Traité médico-philosophique sur l’aliénation mentale*, Paris 1809.

through statistical techniques from the mid-19th century onward – hospitals developed into specialized centers of medical treatment. In this context, introducing statistics into medical practice not only rationalized clinical methods but also contributed significantly to shaping hospitals into rationalized spaces recognizable today. It is therefore reasonable to assert that statistical methods became practical precisely because hospitals consolidated large datasets in one location. Conversely, public health administration demanded increasingly cost-effective strategies, turning to statistical methods to assess expenses relative to outcomes²⁵. As a result, statistics rose to prominence in response to social and economic needs while also redefining those needs, such as efficiency, using new epistemic tools.

As P. Cline Cohen notes, numerization does not just happen on its own; it emerges across multiple interconnected areas through accounting practices. This explains why advocates of numerical medicine, particularly P-C-A. Louis²⁶ and J. Gavarret²⁷, claimed that hospitals naturally provided the conditions needed to apply probability and statistics to clinical work, and therefore to therapeutic results. From a statistical perspective, although the factors influencing specific medical outcomes vary among individual patients – for instance, differences in age or gender – the aggregate of these causes remains sufficiently stable to produce reliable results. Hospitals provided the essential consistency required to facilitate this statistical approach. Concurrently, statistics introduced new conceptual frameworks for understanding illness. Within hospital medicine, statistics reinforced the distinction between a patient's subjective experience and the objective identification of disease. By quantifying abstractions already initiated within pathological anatomy, statistics effectively reduced individual patients to clusters of observable symptoms and clinical signs, which can be termed 'pathological constants'²⁸. Even before the rise of numerical method, J. Tenon had described the many contingences shaping pathological facts as an «embarrassing multiplicity»²⁹, calling for a method that would «reduce everything to general results»³⁰. Thus, from this shared viewpoint, hospitals represented the optimal physical environment for the numerical method to develop.

3. Pierre-Charles-Alexandre Louis and the Numerical School: From Anatomical Pathology to Clinical Statistics

Pierre-Charles-Alexandre Louis was born in Ay in 1787. At the age of twenty, he moved to Reims and began studying medicine. Trained in Paris under

²⁵ See for instance P.J.G Cabanis, *Observation sur les hôpitaux*, Paris 1790.

²⁶ P.-C.-A. Louis, *Research on Phthisis*, Washington 1836.

²⁷ J. Gavarret, *Principes généraux de statistique médicale*, Paris 1840, p. 65.

²⁸ On this, see in particular M. Foucault, *The Birth of The Clinic*.

²⁹ J. Tenon, *Mémoires sur les hôpitaux de Paris*, Paris 1788.

³⁰ *Ibid.*

René Laennec, Louis graduated in 1817 and then practiced medicine in Odessa, where he served as a physician to the Tsar. There, he attended F. Broussais's lectures while working at the Charité Hospital alongside his old friend A. F. Chomel. At the Charité, Louis observed numerous patients and performed countless autopsies, ultimately gathering detailed clinical and post-mortem data on thousands of cases over a seven-year period. In 1825, Louis published his findings in *Researches on Phthisis, Anatomical, Pathological and Therapeutic*³¹. From this study, Louis concluded that comparing groups of patients can shed light on medical questions in ways that examining individual cases – even in large numbers – cannot. This insight became central to his later studies, including *Anatomical, Pathological and Therapeutic Researches upon the Disease Known Under the Name of Gastro-Enteritis, Putrid, Adynamic, Atoxic, or Typhoid Fever* (1829)³². In 1836, Louis published *Researches on the Effects of Bloodletting in Some Inflammatory Diseases, and on the Influence of Tartarized Antimony and Vesication in Pneumonitis*³³, which consolidated his reputation in Paris as the founder of the numerical method and explicitly placed him in opposition to Broussais's physiological school. After many years at the Charité Hospital, Louis eventually transferred to the Hôtel-Dieu and retired from medical practice in the early 1860s.

Doctrinally, Louis emerged as a leading opponent of F. Broussais's theory of inflammation and the broader physiological approach. Louis specifically challenged Broussais's assumption that most diseases originated from localized inflammation of the gastrointestinal tract. Furthermore, he criticized Broussais's frequent application of bloodletting, commonly performed using leeches, due to insufficient empirical evidence supporting its therapeutic efficacy. More broadly, Louis opposed any theoretical framework that avoided systematic data collection and numerical analysis. Louis received his medical education and began practicing medicine in Paris during a complex and relatively understudied historical period following the French Revolution, which had significantly restructured the public healthcare system and its related academic institutions.

At this time, various medical doctrines competed to address one of Europe's most urgent medical challenges: fever epidemics. In the late 18th and early 19th centuries, fevers were widespread and provoked considerable fear among both medical professionals and the general population, attracting significant scholarly attention comparable to contemporary concerns about diseases, such as cancer. Scholars frequently interpreted fevers as various loosely defined inflammatory conditions affecting substantial portions of society. Hygienists theorized that

³¹ P.-C.-A. Louis, *Research on Phthisis*. This work was translated into English by Walshe in 1826 and later by Cowan in 1835.

³² P.-C.-A. Louis, *Anatomical, Pathological and Therapeutic Researches upon the Disease Known Under the Name of Gastro-Enteritis*, Boston 1936. This work was translated in 1936 by Bowditch from French.

³³ P.-C.-A. Louis, *Research on the Effect of Bloodletting*, Boston 1936. This work was translated in 1936 by G.C. Putnam.

fevers disproportionately impacted poorer social groups, resulting in higher mortality rates, although the precise causes of these fevers remained unknown³⁴. In France, diverse medical theories attempted to explain and address these epidemics. Vitalists, influenced by X. Bichat, emphasized nature's mediating role in disease processes. Mechanists, drawing upon the ideas of the Scottish physician J. Brown, as well as physiologists led by F. Broussais, conceptualized inflammation as either an excess or deficiency in the body's internal equilibrium, striving to restore balance through therapeutic interventions. Positivist medicine, closely associated with the physiological school, advocated a systematic and rational analysis of symptoms, aiming to link pathological conditions directly to physiological processes. Ideologists and sensualists, inspired by P-J-G. Cabanis, employed a non-dogmatic empiricism focused on symptom classification. Anatomico-pathological methods, pioneered by R. Laennec and G. L. Bayle, sought to distinguish diseases through precise observation and tracking of lesions and their development; however, merely recording lesions did not sufficiently clarify disease etiology. Concurrently, P. Pinel's nosological school categorized diseases into multiple groups, with Pinel himself identifying seven distinct types of fever³⁵. When Louis began his own research, interest in experimental medicine was only just starting to grow. In 1821, F. Magendie founded the *Journal de Physiologie Expérimentale et Pathologique*, but he did not become professor of experimental physiology at the Collège de France until 1831. As Jean Piquemal correctly observed, none of the medical doctrines of this period adequately resolved the contemporary dilemmas termed the 'crisis of pathological intelligibility' – the inability to fully comprehend disease causation – or the 'crisis of therapeutic rationality' – the difficulty of aligning treatments precisely with outcomes and explaining their mechanisms clearly³⁶.

P-C-A. Louis proposed a way to tackle these issues by introducing what he defined as the numerical method. This approach was grounded in a key principle: integrating anatomical-pathological studies with systematic data collection³⁷. According to Louis, without statistics, there could be no etiology, no effective therapeutic approach, and no meaningful anatomo-pathological inquiry³⁸. Although collecting data to categorize diseases was not entirely unprecedented, Louis's primary innovation was placing systematic data gathering at the very core of medical practice. Contrary to the common practice of assigning data collection tasks to medical students for later review, Louis insisted physicians themselves should directly observe, record, and interpret clinical data³⁹. He first outlined the numerical method in *Généralités sur l'enseignement de la médecine*

³⁴ See in particular the case of Hawkins, *Elements of Medical Statistics*, pp. 43-89.

³⁵ P. Pinel, *La médecine clinique rendue plus précise et plus exacte par l'application de l'analyse*, Paris 1802, p. 432.

³⁶ J. Piquemal, *Essais et leçons d'histoire de la médecine et de la biologie*, Paris 1993, pp. 72-73.

³⁷ P.-C.-A. Louis, *Généralités sur l'enseignement de la médecine Clinique*, 1931 Paris, pp. 10-11.

³⁸ *Ivi*, p. 13.

³⁹ *Ivi*, pp. 6-7; 19.

*clinique*⁴⁰ and further expanded it in *De l'examen des malades et de la recherche des faits généraux*⁴¹. The numerical method, as formulated by Louis, can be summarized in the following three main points:

1. Statistics must be systematically applied as an inductive method.
2. The objective of statistics extends beyond mere description; rather, statistics aims to uncover the natural laws governing vital and pathological phenomena.
3. In Louis's theory, advanced probability theory is not a significant component of statistics. As Canguilhem noted, «Louis never systematically relates statistics to probability theory, as, he merely replaced qualitative adverbs, such as often, frequently, rarely, with numerical ratios»⁴². Indeed, in *Généralités sur l'enseignement de la médecine clinique*, Louis remarked: «When we say, for example, that a symptom frequently occurs in a disease, does that mean we observe it twenty, thirty, forty, sixty, or eighty times out of a hundred? Obviously, we don't know; we use an expression whose value we are unaware of, and which can only be replaced by a more accurate one by counting»⁴³. Nevertheless, asserting that Louis entirely separated statistics from probability would be inaccurate; in later writings, he did consider proportions and frequency in relation to specific symptoms⁴⁴. For him, however, genuine scientific precision meant pinpointing a single outcome linked to a specific cause rather than accounting for a range of probable results⁴⁵. Louis preferred calculating an average outcome of all variations. Unlike Jules Gavarret, Louis did not extensively examine concepts such as confidence intervals⁴⁶.

Leaving aside Louis's well-known contributions to etiology⁴⁷ – such as his clinical definition of typhoid fever (based on characteristic pathological changes in the spleen, mesenteric glands, and Peyer's patches)⁴⁸ and his influential role in limiting the use of bloodletting in treating pulmonary inflammation⁴⁹ – the most significant aspect of his legacy remains the epistemological impact of the numerical method.

⁴⁰ Ivi, pp.19-20.

⁴¹ P.-C.-A. Louis, *De l'examen des malades et de la recherche des faits généraux*, Paris 1837.

⁴² G. Canguilhem, *La statistique médicale*, p. 7.

⁴³ P.-C.-A. Louis, *Généralités*, p. 22.

⁴⁴ «But it is not enough, to assess the value of a symptom in any given disease, to know the proportion of cases in which it occurs; one must also know in which other conditions it appears, and in what proportion; investigate how often it is strong or weak; take into account the constitution of the patients, their age, their sex, their degree of strength or weakness – circumstances that it is impossible to determine accurately without counting» (P.C.A. Louis *Généralités*, p. 24).

⁴⁵ P.-C.-A. Louis, *Research on Phthisis*, p. XXX.

⁴⁶ Ivi, p. 25.

⁴⁷ See on this J. Piquemal, *Essais*.

⁴⁸ P.-C.-A. Louis, *Research on Phthisis*.

⁴⁹ P.-C.-A. Louis, *Research on the Effect of Bloodletting*.

First, Louis conceptualized statistics as a systematic form of data collection capable of revealing underlying laws of pathological frequency. From Louis's perspective, this placed medicine on an equal scientific footing with the natural sciences, particularly chemistry⁵⁰. Medicine, for Louis, possessed its own distinctive laws, but those laws were fundamentally statistical. He perceived himself not merely (using Kantian words) as the 'Newton of the blade of grass' but also as the 'Newton of fevers': medical facts should *emerge*⁵¹ from raw data rather than being shaped by teleological explanations. By excluding teleological interpretations of living organisms – a central concern in contemporary biological debates⁵² – Louis also downplayed qualitative aspects of care, particularly the patient's capacity to develop strategies that might resist purely rational analysis⁵³. Previously, A. Comte had attempted to rationalize – or 'positivize' – medicine, acknowledging its unique character and explicitly referencing Louis's work in his *Cours III* (Lecture 40); however, Comte still advocated specialized methodologies to elevate medicine to a fully positive science⁵⁴. Louis, however, argued that medicine's uniqueness derived not from specialized methodologies but rather from the numerous contingencies and individual clinical cases encountered by physicians – contingencies that, when systematically documented, formed extensive datasets. For Louis, no substantial distinction existed between data gathered from living organisms and those obtained by geologists or chemists. Consequently, any residual vitalism had to yield to rigorous quantification of all disease-related factors, whether objectively measurable – such as frequency of evacuations or body temperature – or inherently subjective – such as pain intensity or general patient experience during illness⁵⁵.

Second, Louis's emphasis on quantification represented both a methodological innovation and a deeper epistemological transformation⁵⁶. In his view, medicine required a redefinition of the relationship between qualitative and quantitative aspects, whereby qualitative elements would be subordinated to quantitative measurement⁵⁷. Everything needed to be measured; nothing was

⁵⁰ P.-C.-A. Louis, *Généralités*.

⁵¹ P.-C.-A. Louis, *Research on Phthisis*, pp. XX-XXI.

⁵² See, for example, M. Mossio *et al.*, *Theoretical principles for biology: Organization*, «Progress in Biophysics and Molecular Biology», 122, 1, 2016, pp. 24-35.

⁵³ G. Canguilhem, *On the Normal and The Pathological*, New York 1991.

⁵⁴ See the 40th lecture of A. Comte, *Cours de philosophie positive III*, Paris 1908 (1838).

⁵⁵ *Ivi*, p. 21.

⁵⁶ If we consider the outcome of this epistemic reduction, we can assert that it is not only an epistemological change but also an ontological one, that is the creation of a new way of vital data to interact with the reality.

⁵⁷ From a historical perspective, this approach may not seem entirely new, given the traditions of positivist and experimental medicine. However, in the philosophy of medicine, it is often – perhaps mistakenly – associated with issues raised by G. Canguilhem in *On the Normal and the Pathological* (). Canguilhem famously critiqued the approaches of Comte's positivist medicine, Broussais's physiological framework, and Claude Bernard's experimental model, all of which view the pathological as a deviation from the normal – a departure from a mathematically defined average endowed with ontological significance. As a result, Canguilhem is often seen as having been the first to claim that a positivist, physiological, and experimental stance in

to lie beyond the domain of numbers and statistics. Referring to the differences and individual circumstances of each patient – differences he insisted should be recorded and made comparable – Louis wrote that «we need to find their value and convert them into signs»⁵⁸. Louis believed that *every* aspect of a patient's life should be collected and categorized, meaning *all* «contingencies» required quantification. He stated the following:

The class of patients they should examine with extreme attention, ascertain their place of birth, and the various places they have subsequently inhabited, inquire into their mode of education and habits of life at all periods of their existence, as also the diseases under which they may at any time have suffered, – note down their temperament, the strength or weakness of their constitution, the slow or rapid course of their disease, etc., etc. Did the patient in any particular instance belong to the working classes, it would be a matter of extreme importance to ascertain at what age he commenced his apprenticeship, and what changes, if any, had occurred in his health from that period; further, whether he had uninterruptedly applied to his trade, or enjoyed intervals of rest from time to time. [...] It is also a matter of extreme importance that the sort of lodging inhabited by patients, and their ordinary diet (especially when they belong to the working classes) should be very carefully noted. The health of the father and mother, and other members of the family, if possible, should also be inquired into with similar care, – in consequence of the apparent reality of hereditary influence on the development of organic diseases, more especially of phthisis, etc., etc.⁵⁹.

Although these data did not initially exist as numerical entities, Louis emphasized the significance of incorporating patient narratives concerning their medical histories. He acknowledged such information as inherently qualitative and value-laden. Nevertheless, by advocating the assignment of numerical values to these qualitative data, Louis effectively proposed that all medically relevant facts should ultimately receive numerical expression. This methodological innovation rested on an ontological assumption rather than solely on an epistemic one, namely, the conviction that qualitative phenomena could be

medicine – one rooted in quantifying pathological states – effectively discards the qualitative dimension. According to this view, a purely quantitative method cannot fully account for the relationship between the normal and the pathological, which is grounded in the living organism's *normativity* – its ability to generate its own norms – and its capacity to interact with the environment. Contrary to the most common reading of Canguilhem, however, I suggest that he offered another possible interpretation. In his account, the positivists did not attempt to reduce the qualitative to the quantitative outright; rather, they presumed the qualitative to be epistemically irrelevant. In *On the Normal and the Pathological*, Canguilhem himself hints at this in the chapter on the implications of Comte, Broussais, and Bernard, noting: «Quantity is a denied quality, but not a suppressed quality» (G. Canguilhem, *On the Normal and the Pathological*, p. 58). In other words, to secure the 'positivity' of medicine – ensuring it meets a certain standard of scientificity – positivists set the qualitative aside and focused exclusively on quantitative data, rather than eliminating the qualitative entirely. For example, É. Littré's efforts were precisely aimed at sidelining, obscuring, and effectively bypassing the qualitative dimension.

⁵⁸ P.-C.-A. Louis, *Généralités*, p. 16. This underscores the ongoing challenge in modern biomedicine: the difficulty of quantifying and extracting meaningful data from all aspects of a patient's life. See the description given by the European Union of [Personalised Medicine](https://health.ec.europa.eu/medicinal-products/personalised-medicine_en) https://health.ec.europa.eu/medicinal-products/personalised-medicine_en.

⁵⁹ P.-C.-A. Louis, *Research on Phthisis*, p. XVI.

rendered homogeneous with quantitative data by transforming the former into the latter. Louis's Swiss student, M. J. d'Espine, echoed this stance in his work on *Orchite*, in which he proposed converting any kind of data (including pain intensity) into numbers⁶⁰.

Finally, Louis's method implied the loss of patient individuality – patient individuality, that Canguilhem later defined as the patient's normativity. According to this perspective, patients ceased to represent distinct individuals capable of developing unique adaptive responses to illness; instead, they became anonymous cases within larger groups. Louis explicitly stated: «Once the exact facts have been gathered, they must be grouped together, uniting those which, through their similarity, indicate the same condition, and separating those that display opposing characteristics»⁶¹.

By collecting detailed patient data and subsequently quantifying and depersonalizing them, Louis transformed individual patients into cases belonging to specific pathological categories. Thus, patients effectively became identified with their illnesses, thereby completing the abstraction process. Louis regarded medicine's fundamental challenge not as providing treatments tailored to the unique peculiarities of individual patients but as creating uniform, universally valid treatments applicable to clearly defined pathological categories. According to Louis, once a sufficiently precise category had been established, individual patient treatment would naturally follow. He maintained that physicians should assign patients to these categories – or fit illnesses into them – provided these classifications accommodated the full spectrum of patient data. Thus, the systematic classification of every symptom within each group was necessary. Louis envisioned the physician's role as thoroughly collecting patient information to reveal coherent and standardized pathological patterns.

When we consider Louis's ideas on classification, on the one hand, they mirror the objectives of personalized medicine, which relies on highly detailed subcategories built from large volumes of patient data. On the other hand, they share key features with population-based epidemiology, which focuses on the larger population rather than the individual patient: Louis's theory centers on exploring the causes of *incidence* rather than the individual causes of an illness, aiming instead to identify frequency-based laws. As the next section will show, it was precisely in therapy that Louis's numerical approach encountered its most intense criticisms in France and found its strongest supporters in North America.

⁶⁰ M. J. d'Espine, *Mémoire analytique sur l'orchite blennorrhagique* in *Mémoires de la société médicale d'observation 1*, Paris 1837, pp. 412-495.

⁶¹ P.-C.-A. Louis, *Généralités*, p. 21.

3. From Louis's Influence and Its Eclipse in France

3.1 Louis in France: From Therapeutics to Clinical Epidemiology – J. Gavarret as the Link

In the 1830s and 1840s, Louis had a significant impact on French medicine. The creation of the Société Médicale d'Observation de Paris in 1832 by his disciples – Bizot and d'Espine from Geneva, Barth, Baumgarten, and Bondin from France, and Jackson from the United States – demonstrates the broad reach of his ideas. Similar societies soon formed in Boston and Philadelphia. During this time, many physicians endorsed numerism. Among them were A. F. Chomel, A. Velpeau, P. Rayer, J. Capuron, A. Trousseau, A. Le Pelletier, J. P. Bouillaud, and G. Andral. Although they supported the doctrine, they did not all embrace it fully⁶². However, J. Gavarret, a strong admirer of Louis's work, applied Louis's numerical medicine to a more systematic framework. In his *Principes généraux de statistique médicale*, set out to demonstrate how to apply probability theory systematically to medicine. Building on the work of P. S. Laplace and S. D. Poisson, he refined Louis's method by introducing the use of confidence intervals and calculating the probability that differences in relative frequencies were statistically significant⁶³. Gavarret argued that early proponents of numerism had largely ignored the importance of probability calculations, concentrating instead on comparing data to yield «certain results»⁶⁴. He thus called for a thorough application of probability theory in medicine, introducing the law of large numbers into the clinical research. In response to critics who felt Louis's statistical method was unsuited to medicine, Gavarret developed strategies for handling random variables, ensuring that certain conditions did indeed remain constant. Still, he never doubted the existence of underlying natural laws in medical phenomena⁶⁵.

Like Louis, Gavarret maintained that hospitals represented the ideal setting for ensuring invariant conditions because only hospitals could provide sufficiently large datasets for robust statistical analysis. Indeed, Gavarret strongly supported a population-based approach, advising that «doctors who embark on substantial scientific endeavors should exclusively conduct their research in hospitals»⁶⁶. By adapting the concept of large numbers to clinical practice, he concluded that reliable statistics required at least 500 cases. Hospitals not only made it possible to gather samples of this size but also helped identify confounding factors that could otherwise distort statistical results.

⁶² For a more comprehensive list, see G. Canguilhem, *La statistique*, pp. 9-11, and Piquemal *Essais*, p. 83.

⁶³ J. Gavarret, *Principes*, p. 110. In addition, Gavarret mentioned A. Quetelet only once (p. 59), despite Quetelet's key influence on positivism in the 19th century. This omission underscores the distance between numerical and positivist medicine.

⁶⁴ *Ivi*, p. 139.

⁶⁵ *Ivi*, pp. 119-125.

⁶⁶ *Ivi*, p. 118.

In an effort to improve the reliability of statistical observations, Gavarret recommended first calculating statistical frequencies and then using a significance test to compare two therapies – one guided by frequency data and one omitting it¹. Even Louis – though lacking Gavarret’s mathematical framework – had previously suggested dividing patients into large groups and administering different therapies to each². In this sense, Louis anticipated the controlled clinical trials central to contemporary evidence-based medicine, especially randomized controlled trials that now constitute its methodological foundation. Louis implicitly proposed randomization to minimize bias and the establishment of control groups for comparative analysis – ideas Gavarret would later reinforce with mathematical justifications³. While adapting Louis’s methods, Gavarret remained committed to integrating qualitative and quantitative data, although he approached it using probabilistic rather than strictly statistical means. Nevertheless, the underlying epistemological framework remained consistent with that of Louis. Gavarret upheld Louis’s key principle that data must be standardized for comparisons to be valid, noting that «we encounter variety in the details, but consistency in the whole»⁴. He showed that Louis’s effort to convert qualitative data into quantitative form was even more convincing when framed by probabilistic laws⁵. From Gavarret’s viewpoint, however, medicine’s qualitative data could not always be precisely quantified, and it frequently required representation through ranges rather than exact numerical values.

Despite these contributions, numerical medicine’s adherents did not fully embrace Gavarret’s probabilistic approach, resulting in little immediate alteration of Louis’s original doctrine. Nevertheless, Gavarret exerted a considerable influence on epidemiology, even though his own research gradually shifted away from probability-based studies in his later career⁶. Unsurprisingly, statistical medicine gradually shifted focus from therapeutics to clinical epidemiology, where it found a lasting niche in 19th century⁷.

¹ Ivi, pp. 156-157.

² P.-C.-A. Louis, *On the Bloodletting*.

³ For Louis’s relationship with evidence-based medicine see A. Morabia; D.L. Sackett *et al.*, *Evidence-Based Medicine: What It Is and What It Isn’t*, «British Medical Journal», 312, 1966, pp. 71-72, for the manifesto of evidence-based medicine that defines the randomized controlled trial as the gold standard for this approach.

⁴ J. Gavarret, *Principes*, p. 121.

⁵ Ivi, pp. 5-11.

⁶ For an overview see U. Tröhler, *The French Road to Gavarret’s clinical application of probabilistic thinking Part 2: Louis-Denis-Jules Gavarret*, «Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine», 113, 9, 2020, pp. 360-366.

⁷ A. Morabia, *La convergence historique de l’épidémiologie et de la médecine clinique, de Pierre Louis à l’AMBRE*, in A. Fagot-Largeault (a cura di), *L’émergence de la médecine scientifique*, Paris 2012, pp. 77-97.

3.2 Criticisms and Debate on Numerical Medicine During Louis's Time

During Louis's lifetime, numerical medicine was not considered the gold standard for clinical practice despite the significance of Louis's critical and empirical contributions. Louis's critique of bloodletting – outlined in his work *On Bloodletting*⁸ – helped to diminish the strong influence of Broussais's physiological doctrine in France. Furthermore, Louis maintained a strong reputation among his students, as evidenced by the active discussions among his French and numerous international pupils⁹. Consequently, it remains necessary to explain why Louis's doctrine is relatively unknown in contemporary France. This lack of recognition is not recent. Typically, medical dictionaries recognize Louis solely as the physician who first identified lesions specific to typhoid fever, distinguishing this disease from other illnesses frequently confused with it at that time. Indeed, the numerical method had already begun to lose visibility shortly after Louis's death in 1872. For instance, the *Littré-Robin* medical dictionary devotes only a brief passage to the numerical method, explicitly asserting that statistical analysis should not replace other medical observation methods and describing it merely as an auxiliary tool¹⁰. Likewise, in *Médecine et Médecins*, É. Littré makes only a brief reference to Louis regarding the typhoid fever, maintaining that no one has yet discovered a reliable way to identifying its etiology¹¹. Even more revealing is G. Vapereau's *Dictionnaire*, which promises to list «all notable persons of France and foreign countries»¹² while omitting any mention of Louis and the numerical method.

I propose two main reasons why Louis's work was neglected. First, the historical context played a significant role. In the second half of the 19th century, two strongly experimental paradigms emerged in France – experimental medicine and microbiology – ‘clashing’ with Louis's statistical-observational approach. These two paradigms not only conflicted with Louis's numerical approach but also pushed it aside and established themselves as the leading methodological framework.

Second, academic factors contributed substantially to Louis's limited influence. Louis never received a university professorship, and neither did his French students. This circumstance prevented his doctrine from becoming formally integrated into academic curricula, in marked contrast to figures such as C. Bernard and the positivists. In particular, in his *Cours de Philosophie Positive*, A. Comte vehemently rejected deterministic and reductionist approaches in the life sciences. For Comte, statistical approaches exemplified precisely the type of reductionism he opposed. He insisted strongly on differentiating the study

⁸ P.-C.-A. Louis, *On the Bloodletting*.

⁹ See W. Osler, *The influence of Louis on American medicine*, and M. Greenwood, *Louis and the Numerical Method*, in *The Medical Dictator and Other Biographical Studies*, London 1936.

¹⁰ É. Littré, C. Robin, *Dictionnaire de médecine, chirurgie, pharmacie*, Paris 1873, p. 1130.

¹¹ É. Littré, *Médecine et médecins*, Paris 1872, p. 227.

¹² G. Vapereau, *Dictionnaire universel des contemporains*, Paris 1893.

of living organisms from disciplines such as geometry, physics, and astronomy. According to Comte, «As an inevitable consequence of its characteristic complexity [...] the study of living bodies directly rejects in two different ways any real use of mathematical procedures». When discussing «vital phenomena», he claimed that «their extreme diversity and inextricable multiplicity could in no way allow our weak intelligence to effectively pursue their logical combinations»¹³. Comte thus concluded that the numerical could not be applied to biology or medicine: «Such complexity even radically opposes the possibility that these elementary laws could ever be mathematically revealed. [...] For these laws could become accessible only through the immediate analysis of their numerical effects»¹⁴. Given the countless variables at play when studying living beings, he declared that «no idea of fixed numbers, let alone numerical laws, and especially mathematical investigation, can be considered compatible with the fundamental character of biological research»¹⁵.

Following a Bichatian framework, A. Comte aligned himself with critics who opposed numerical medicine¹⁶ characterizing Louis's statistical approach as crude empiricism, an «absolute empiricism disguised under frivolous mathematical appearances»¹⁷ unsuitable for examining disease. Comte argued that by reducing therapeutics purely to numerical data, Louis's method essentially abandoned induction in medicine, leading to what Comte considered «an aberration as profoundly irrational». As a result, Comte excluded statistics from the study of living organisms, dismissing it as «vain and puerile efforts to determine, according to their illusory theory of chances, the number of cases appropriate to legitimize each of these statistical indications»¹⁸.

Comte's critical viewpoint was widely echoed during the 19th century. In 1837, François-Joseph Double published an influential article entitled *The Inapplicability of Statistics to the Practice of Medicine*, expressing similar skepticism. That same year, Antonio Risueño presented analogous arguments before the Royal Academy of Medicine¹⁹. Later, in 1865, C. Bernard reinforced this stance in his *An Introduction to the Study of Experimental Medicine*²⁰, while C. Lasègue offered a more moderate but still critical view in his *Études Médicales*²¹.

Lasègue, for instance, recognized Louis as one of the significant medical innovators of a difficult historical period but believed that the latter had committed a fundamental error. Rather than emphasizing pathology, Louis attempted to create a rational therapeutic approach by borrowing methodologies from the natural sciences, thereby constructing a flawless yet unrealistic physiology.

¹³ A. Comte, *Cours*, p. 218.

¹⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁵ *Ivi*, p. 219.

¹⁶ See for instance the criticism of A. Risueño in the next pages.

¹⁷ *Ibid.*

¹⁸ *Ivi*, p. 220.

¹⁹ A. Risueño, *Mémoire sur le calcul des probabilités appliqué à la médecine*, Paris 1837.

²⁰ C. Bernard, *An Introduction to the Study of Experimental Medicine*, Paris 1949, p. 14.

²¹ C. Lasègue, *Études médicales*, Paris 1884.

According to Lasègue, the numerical method sought to eliminate any value-laden aspects from clinical observation. He maintained that a physician's observation depends on three factors: sensitivity (the observer's perceptual capability), the material object being observed, and the observer's intentionality or agency shaped by personal and psychological motivations²². These value-laden elements, he argued, cannot be eliminated from observation because they stem from a *parti pris* – essentially a standpoint²³. Anticipating concepts similar to those later articulated in standpoint theory, Lasègue suggested that Louis's pursuit of absolute objectivity would not enhance scientific rigor but would instead weaken the validity and legitimacy of clinical observation. Lasègue warned that ignoring the observer's perspective would inevitably result in an unstructured accumulation of data lacking coherent logic, thus reducing clinical practice to a mechanical activity. In his assessment, this loss of perspective removes causality from a physician's conclusions, leaving only «chains of coincidences»²⁴ – what we might today recognize as the purely correlative pitfalls of machine-driven analysis.

A. de Risueño articulated similar concerns in his *Mémoire*, in which he criticized the numerical model for importing mechanistic frameworks from the natural sciences in an attempt to establish scientific validity in medicine²⁵. For Risueño, the issue was both epistemological and ontological, as living organisms cannot simply be treated as physical or chemical entities. In his view, the investigation of life required moving beyond the forms of certainty achievable in mathematical sciences and embracing a precision that accounted for the inherent variability and continual transformation of living organisms. Although Risueño did not explicitly endorse metaphysical vitalism – defined as the belief in a unique vital force distinguishing living from non-living matter – he nevertheless insisted upon a specialized methodological approach suited specifically to the life sciences. C. Wolfe and colleagues have later defined a similar perspective as «attitudinal vitalism» indicating that this stance does not assert a specific ontological status for life but rather concerns the manner in which researchers approach its study – the attitude itself²⁶.

From Risueño's viewpoint, an independent method in the life sciences preserves the patient's individuality: «The problem of the numerists is not to cure this or that patient, but to cure as many as possible out of a given total»²⁷. Building on this criticism, Risueño further questioned the conception of causality implicit in numerical medicine. He argued that if numerical medicine assumes comparability among patients and diseases, then determining disease

²² The psychological foundation of needs is a well-developed concept in France. For example, see the university manual *Besoins et Tendances*, edited by G. Canguilhem for PUF.

²³ C. Lasègue, *Études médicales*, p. 169.

²⁴ *Ivi*, p. 175.

²⁵ A. Risueño, *Mémoire*, p. 34.

²⁶ C. T. Wolfe *et al.*, *What Kind of Vitalism in 'The Normal and the Pathological?*, in P. O. Méthot. and J. Sholl (eds.), *Vital Norms*, Paris 2020, pp. 219-250.

²⁷ A. Risueño, *Mémoire*, p. 33.

etiology becomes secondary to evaluating treatment effectiveness. According to this reasoning, understanding precisely why a particular therapy works becomes less important than the empirical observation that it succeeds in most cases. Risueño claimed that genuine induction can only happen when we compare similar qualities while still retaining the unique, defining features of each element. By contrast, numerical medicine transforms these qualities into numerical quantities, subsequently aggregating them into homogeneous groups where formerly qualitative features become quantitatively comparable. He firmly insisted that in medicine «number as such means nothing» because «the number – or quantity – of a fact can never reveal its nature or quality»²⁸. In other words, without safeguarding the qualitative dimension, we can't preserve real induction – seen as the bedrock of medicine's scientific nature – or maintain the patient's individuality.

Similarly, in *The American Journal of the Medical Sciences*, Doublet criticized Louis for essentially replacing inductive reasoning with arithmetic calculations and logic²⁹. Doublet's argument, representative of broader criticisms at the time, maintained that statistical induction did not constitute true induction and therefore could establish only correlations rather than genuine causal relationships. From Doublet's perspective, Louis's approach risked directing medicine toward mechanization. In addition, Doublet expressed concern about the implications of this mechanization for clinical practice, arguing that the «tendency toward rationalization» had been amplified by hospitalization and hospital-based medical training. He thought that numerical medicine might overshadow the «needs of the patient»³⁰, warning that hospital organization promoted a clinical practice focused on data-gathering rather than actual patient care. According to Doublet, hospitals had replaced physicians' capacities for prioritizing and interpreting clinical data, grounded in personal expertise, with a narrowly focused emphasis on data accumulation³¹. Applying statistics in this manner, Doublet argued, prevents doctors from assigning different degrees of importance to data depending on each patient's unique circumstances. As a result, Louis's method overlooks the patient's individuality – the unique combination of data each patient provides – and these data, according to Doublet, hold distinct qualitative value for each person. Thus, depersonalizing the patient is inherently linked to what he defined as numeration of patients³². Indeed, Doublet maintained that each patient should be considered as «a unique and distinct challenge»³³ rather than a sum of standardized data. Anticipating contemporary ethical debates on statistics in biomedicine, Doublet questioned

²⁸ Ivi, p. 109.

²⁹ M. Double, *The inapplicability of statistics to the practice of medicine*, «The American Journal of the Medical Sciences», 21, 1837, pp. 247-250.

³⁰ Ivi, p. 246.

³¹ See also J. Piquemal, *Essais*, p. 85.

³² See also A.J. Bollet, *Pierre Louis: the numerical method and the foundation of quantitative medicine*, «American Journal of Medicine Science», 266, 2, 1973, pp. 92-101.

³³ M. Double, *The inapplicability of statistics*, p. 246.

whether clinical science could depend exclusively on statistical calculations, given the inherent difficulty of capturing each patient's uniqueness using statistics. This difficulty arises from the assumption that statistical analysis must operate according to broadly defined natural laws³⁴.

3.3 A Possible Connection: Louis's Legacy in North America and Its Impact on Contemporary Medicine

Numerical medicine did not gain significant acceptance in France after the death of Louis. Instead, during the 19th century, it developed along a distinct trajectory in the United States. As W. Osler's article *The Influence of Louis on American Medicine*³⁵ clearly recounts, Louis's ideas spread most extensively in North America. This diffusion occurred primarily because numerous physicians who trained under Louis in Paris, either as students or specialists, were American. Upon returning to their country, these physicians introduced Louis's methods into American medical practice, greatly influencing contemporary North American medicine. This development had two key outcomes.

First, it produced a generation of American physicians who were trained in the numerical method and who not only used it but over time further refined it.

Second, it firmly established Louis's numerical approach within American medical education and research institutions. Harvard Medical School notably emerged as a crucial center for this development, largely through influential figures such as W. W. Gerhard, J. Jackson Jr., and O. W. Holmes. Gerhard, a physician based in Philadelphia, was among the first to employ Louis's statistical methods to differentiate typhoid fever from typhus, thereby demonstrating the effectiveness of numerical reasoning in differential diagnosis³⁶. Jackson Jr., a leading physician in Boston, integrated Louis's principles into his clinical teaching, stressing the importance of systematic data collection for medical decision-making³⁷. Supported by his father, James Jackson Sr., an influential figure at Harvard, Jackson Jr. successfully promoted a quantitative, evidence-driven approach within Harvard's medical curriculum. Holmes, who served both as professor and subsequently Dean at Harvard Medical School, actively advocated for the numerical method, insisting on rigorous empirical verification in clinical practice.

In his well-known essay of 1842, *Homeopathy and Its Kindred Delusions*³⁸, Holmes extended the same skepticism he had toward non-evidence-based medicine such as homeopathy to other unproven treatments. Holmes advocated strongly for a scientifically grounded approach to therapeutics based explicitly

³⁴ Ivi, p. 247.

³⁵ W. Osler, *The influence of Louis*.

³⁶ W.W. Gerhard, *On Thyphus fever*.

³⁷ J. Jackson Jr., *Cases of Cholera Collected*.

³⁸ O.W. Holmes, *Homeopathy and its kindred delusions*, Boston 1842.

on Louis's statistical methods. In his *The Contagiousness of Puerperal Fever*³⁹, he argued that childbed fever was being transmitted by physicians through contaminated hands and instruments – an insight that anticipated both modern evidence-based medicine and then later established randomized controlled trials as the gold standard in clinical research. His work also laid the early foundations for epidemiological thinking, ultimately supported by I. Semmelweis.

With the institutionalization of numerical medicine in North America⁴⁰, I suggest that the epistemological rupture introduced by the numerical school influenced many contemporary biomedical approaches that rely heavily on statistics. Three key elements of numerical medicine in particular remain relevant today. Here, I will briefly consider them, leaving a deeper analysis for the future.

First, statistical medicine posited data collection as the sole model for achieving scientific validity: the more data one collects, the more precise the results⁴¹. This principle directly underlies Personalized Medicine⁴², which aims to gather as much *meaningful* data as possible on each patient, covering various dimensions of the patient's life⁴³. The goal is to administer the right drug, at the right dose, to the right patient, at the right time⁴⁴. However, critics such as N. Rose warn that this approach risks 'naturalizing' medicine in a way that mirrors Louis's critics in his own era: whereas Louis sought exhaustive data from chemical analyses, contemporary researchers rely on genetics and other omics methodologies, reflecting a similar ambition for comprehensive information⁴⁵.

Second, numerical medicine heavily emphasized comparing groups of patients undergoing different treatments, as exemplified by Louis's research on bloodletting. According to A. Morabia, Louis was the first to understand the importance of randomization, which is now central to Evidence-Based Medicine⁴⁶. Morabia also suggests that Louis was the first to tackle the issue of confounding variables – factors that could bias results because of uncontrollable differences between the groups being compared. Louis thereby introduced a methodological innovation integrating clinical research and therapeutic decision-making, possibly explaining why contemporary epidemiologists frequently reference Louis more than clinicians do⁴⁷.

³⁹ O. W. Holmes, *The Contagiousness of Puerperal Fever*.

⁴⁰ See W. Osler, *The influence of Louis*, and M. Corteel, *Le hasard et le pathologique*, Paris 2020, for a discussion on Louis's theory circulation.

⁴¹ J. Gavarret, *Principes*.

⁴² L. H. Goetz and N. J. Schork. *Personalized medicine: motivation, challenges, and progress*, «Fertil Steril», 2018, 109, 6, pp. 952-996.

⁴³ M. Panahiazar et al., *Empowering Personalized Medicine with Big Data and Semantic Web Technology*, «Proceedes IEEE Int Conf Big Data» October, pp. 790-795.

⁴⁴ K.K. Jain, *Textbook of Personalized Medicine*, Dordrecht 2009.

⁴⁵ N. Rose, *Personalized Medicine: Promises and Perils of a New Paradigm for Health-care*, «Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences», 77, 2013, pp. 341-352.

⁴⁶ A. Morabia, *La convergence historique*.

⁴⁷ A. Morabia, *P.-C.-A. Louis and the birth of clinical epidemiology*, «J. Clin. Epidemiol.», 49, 12, 1996, pp.1327-1333.

Third, from a population epidemiology standpoint, numerical medicine adapted the ideas championed by 19th-century hygienists (still foundational in modern epidemiology) and applied them to clinical practice. Louis proposed that treatments should address population-level causes of disease incidence rather than individual cases alone. This involved analyzing frequencies of pathological occurrences across various demographic groups based on gender, age, social class, and other relevant factors.

All these innovations derive fundamentally from Louis's crucial methodological shift: the translation of qualitative medical observations into quantitative data, which Louis described as «transforming qualities into numbers»⁴⁸. However, this transformation raises a critical epistemological question regarding numerical medicine: Is it genuinely possible to eliminate qualitative elements entirely? Jacques Bizot, a student of Louis, openly acknowledged the practical impossibility of fully replacing qualitative assessments with strictly quantitative measures. Regardless of how systematically physicians documented lesions or carefully collected clinical data to identify consistent disease markers, they inevitably confronted an essential characteristic of living beings – what Canguilhem later defined as *vital normativity*⁴⁹. In medicine, certain anomalies cause no functional harm; they are difficult to categorize and resist being used as building blocks for generalized pathological constants⁵⁰.

4. Conclusion

In this article, I argued that Pierre-Charles-Alexandre Louis's systematic application of statistics in medicine introduced an epistemological rupture in the field. This development raises a long-standing issue regarding the role of statistics within the life sciences, in both past and contemporary contexts: specifically, whether it is possible to fully eliminate qualitative dimensions from patient-related data. Historically, statistical approaches in medicine can be traced at least as far back as the 17th and 18th centuries. Scholars such as W. Petty, J. Graunt, and J. Jurin employed quantitative methods to analyze mortality patterns and to improve smallpox prevention. Nonetheless, these initial efforts remained largely descriptive, falling short of establishing a scientific standard.

A significant shift occurred in the early 19th century, when Louis's numerical school turned statistics into an analytical tool. I showed that Louis's numerical medicine arose from the particular conditions of 19th-century France, especially the organizational structure of public healthcare. At that time, hospitals served the dual function of public health institutions and educational facilities. This dual role created an ideal context for numerical medicine

⁴⁸ W. R. Steiner, *Dr. Pierre-Chalres-Alexandre Louis*, p. 451.

⁴⁹ G. Canguilhem, *On the Normal and The Pathological*.

⁵⁰ J. Bizot, *Recherches sur le Cœur et le système artériel chez l'homme*, in *Société Médicale d'Observation*, Paris 1837, p. 271, see the «Avertissement»; see also Piquemal, *Essais*, p. 88.

by enabling patient grouping, systematic data collection, and standardized treatment methods. On the one hand, the application of statistical approaches corresponded with broader tendencies toward economic rationalization, which increased healthcare efficiency. On the other hand, it reshaped clinical medicine and reconceptualized hospitals as rationalized research environments. Later, probability-based techniques were employed in attempts to further legitimize abstracting patient experiences into pathological constants. I suggested that Louis promoted his numerical method as a response to the therapeutic crisis caused by fever epidemics in France. At that time, prevailing medical doctrines – such as vitalism, mechanism, positivist medicine, and nosology – failed either to explain disease etiology clearly or to propose effective therapeutic interventions. Rather than relying purely on descriptive or observational approaches or fully adopting probabilistic methods, Louis focused on systematic data gathering, quantitative categorization, and frequency analysis to identify disease patterns. His approach directly opposed teleological interpretations of illness and favored instead a naturalistic model based on data analysis, mirroring contemporary approaches in chemistry and physics.

Louis's method required the quantification of all aspects of patient histories, including demographic data, living conditions, lifestyle, and even qualitative descriptions of pain. This quantification allowed clinical cases to be standardized effectively. However, such standardization involved translating qualitative information into numerical data, resulting in diminished individual specificity in favor of more precise classification. Critics of Louis's approach, including M. Double, A. Risueño, C. Bernard and A. Comte, argued that numerical medicine was excessively reductionist. They claimed it failed to account for the complexity inherent in living systems, depersonalized patient care, and transformed medicine into mere data collection rather than a pursuit of causal explanations. Although Louis's numerical method did not gain wide acceptance in France, it took hold in 19th-century America. Numerous American physicians who trained in Paris brought his methods back and integrated them into their clinical work. Consequently, a generation of American physicians emerged who were proficient in statistical methods, ultimately contributing to the institutionalization of numerical medicine, particularly at Harvard Medical School. Influential figures such as W. W. Gerhard, J. Jackson Jr., and O. W. Holmes applied Louis's principles in differential diagnosis, teaching, and early epidemiological research. These contributions firmly established an empirical, data-driven approach to medicine.

In fact, several essential components of Louis's numerical method – particularly group comparisons among patients, randomization in clinical trials, and patient classification aimed at understanding disease incidence – continue to underpin contemporary biomedical practices. For this reason, examining Louis's theory is valuable, both historically and philosophically. Indeed, the challenges and opportunities identified by Louis in the 19th century concerning statistical

methods still profoundly shape ongoing debates regarding the application of big data in contemporary medicine.

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